

Broken Bonds: How Globalization Conceptualizations and Languages Transformed Experiences in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: The world is without doubt undergoing tremendous social, economic, political and technological transformation. These developments have resulted in fundamental changes in the nature, structure, and capacity of nation states and their relationships inter se, and with the component units in a State. Over the years, there has also been increased interaction between people from different countries facilitated by the tremendous improvements in Communications. Economic transactions can be concluded between persons in different countries without seeing each other. While these changes are not necessarily novel, they have shown the dynamism inherent in society. The changes have come to be generally referred to loosely as ‘globalization’ which is today one of the defining features of the contemporary world. Due to its amorphous and uncertain nature, globalization has become one of the most pervasive, but deeply contested processes and developments in present-day society. The fact that it is a ‘process’ makes it difficult for anyone to correctly predict its entire scope, contours and even destination. It is on this score that today every socio-economic and even political problem and development is attributed either directly or indirectly to globalization. This paper adopted doctrinal research methodology, and found that globalization affects humanity. Globalization poses a lot of challenges to humanity and for these challenges to be adequately addressed, policy makers must therefore, widen their horizons so as to arrive at carefully considered policies, legislations and judicial decisions.

KEYWORDS: Globalization, Political, Economical, Social

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Globalization as a phenomenon, being universal by its nature and character, covers not only the global economy, finance and mass media, where it manifests itself in the most developed form, but also in other spheres of social life, including law. At the same time, the impact of global factors significantly affects the essential and substantive aspects of the state’s legal system and humanity. Globalization was first used in a publication titled, ‘Towards New Education in the year 1930’ to denote a comprehensive outlook on human experience in education. However, it was not until the 1960s that the term began to be widely used by economists and other social scientists. The United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia defines globalization as a widely used term that can be defined in a number of different ways. When used in an economic sense, it refers to the reduction and removal of barriers between national borders in order to facilitate the flow of goods, capital, services and labour. One of the consequences of such process is that the distinction between domestic and foreign domains is becoming more insignificant since there is an acceleration of economic integration and interdependence of countries. In a literal sense, globalization is the process of globalizing, transformation of some things or phenomena into global ones.

2.0. CONCEPTUALIZATION AND CONSEQUENCES

It can be described as a process by which the people of the world are united into a single society and function together. This process is a combination of economic, technological, social cultural and political forces. By this definition, this paper cannot but agree with the views of Britton who maintains that there are three principal catalysts of globalization, namely; technological factors, economic factors and political factors.¹ Hence, the internet which was created in 1973 by the United States Defence Advanced Research Project Agency has resulted in an explosion in global communication and information. It is now possible to instantaneously transmit information around the globe via technological process such as email and instant messaging. Again through satellite technology, events occurring in distant countries are viewed worldwide by people who have access to internet, cable or satellite television service. Economic factors are also viewed as catalyst for globalization. Thus, the creation of institutions like the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development and the International Monetary Fund are on the front burner of lending to nation states, thus providing the framework for international commerce and finance which will help the economies of nation states to develop. Furthermore, it can be argued that one of the most significant factors in the creation of

¹ S. Britton. *The impact of Globalization and its Consequences for the Individual and Society at* <http://www.articlealley.com-1595422-22> last accessed on 22/4/2025.

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globalization has been the political factor. Apart from facilitating the Bretton Woods Conferences where the plans for the world financial framework were created, globalization currently is related to political changes across the globe, for instance, the collapse of the Soviet Union. Without free market forces operating in Russia, the economy was unable to develop significantly. Since the collapse of communism, Russia has been integrated into the global community and has been seen as a valuable trading partner with its vast oil reserves.

This goes to explain that the discourse on globalization is complicated with far-reaching consequences on national and international legislations and policies with regard to social economic and political issues. The phrase global village is often used to illustrate the outcome of globalization whereby through the process of technology like the use of internet, where one has all been linked on one global entity. No wonder Britton in agreement with Giddens sees globalization as the intensification of worldwide social relations which link distant localities in such a way that local happenings are shaped by events occurring many miles away and this involves a change in the way that one appears to understand geography and experience localness. In other words, one of the consequences of globalization is that there is no longer in existence a place called abroad² since the world has become a global village. For Herman,³ the terms globalization and internationalization are often used interchangeably. However, the learned author attempted an investigation into the difference between the two concepts. For him, internationalization connotes relevance of international trade, relations, agreements (treaties) etc. International signifies the relation between or among states while the concept of globalization means the elimination of national barriers for economic purpose.

In the light of the foregoing, 'globalization' is most often used to apply to economic globalization which is the integration of national economies into the international economy through trade, foreign direct investment, capital flows, migration and the spread of technology. It therefore means that globalization in its economic sense is the global integration of economies worldwide. In this sense, world economy is seen as a single market.⁴ In spite of this economic sense of globalization, the term broadly refers to the expansion of global linkage, the organization of social life in a global scale and the growth of a global consciousness, hence to the consolidation of world society.

The term 'globalization' pervades the expression of political scholars as well as legal practitioners.⁵ Globalization refers to the present, but it is also vital to highlight that the phenomena it describes are scarcely new.⁶ Globalization has been depicted as 'a new, complex, dynamic, multidimensional, and worldwide phenomenon, which means different things to different people and different things to the same people across time and space.'⁷ It refers to the growing tendency of interactions, interconnection and integration of countries on a global scale.

Globalization according to Nsibambi is a process of advancement and increase in interaction among world's countries and people facilitated by progressive technology changes in locomotion, communication, laws, governance, political and military power, knowledge and skills as well as interfacing of culture and value system.⁸ In other words, globalization is not a value-free, innocent, self-determining process. It is an international, legal, socio-political economic and cultural permeation process facilitated by policies of government, private cooperation, international agencies and civil society organizations. It essentially seeks to enhance and deploy a country's economic, political, technological, ideological, legal and military power and influence for competitive domination in the world.

3.0. HISTORICAL EVOLUTION: ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES

Another important stage in the history of Globalization is the Islamic Golden Age. During this period, there was an establishment of a sustained economy across the old world between Jewish and Muslim traders and explorers which resulted in the globalization of crops, trades, knowledge and technology. The advent of the Mongol Empire⁹ and the so called *PaxMongolica* of the 13th century had several other remarkable globalizing consequences, such as the creation of the first international postal service.

² See P.Yain, *The End of Foreign Policy, Global Interests, Global Linkages and National Limits* (Green Alliance Publications, 2001). See also J. Eleonu, *The Opportunities and Dangers of Globalization towards the protection of Human Rights* (2022/23) (9) *Journal of Law and Contemporary Law*: 88-94.

³ Available at <<http://www.websites-online-dictionary.org>> last accessed on 24/3/2025.

⁴ D. J. C. Fong et al; "Globalization: Access to justice – International Covenants and Protection of Native Rights" available at <<http://www.sociology.emory.edu/globalization/issues01.html>> last accessed on 19/4/2025.

⁵ J. Delbruck, 'Globalization of Law, Politics, and Markets – Implications for Domestic Law: A European perspective' (1993) (1) (2) *Indian Journal of Global Legal Studies*: 1.

⁶ S. Dauda and R. Onya, *Third World in Global Politics* (Tabith Publishers Ltd. 2017) 174.

⁷ E.E. Ogbadu and A.A. Ameh, 'Globalization and Nigeria's Involvement in International Marketing' (2012) (2) *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*: 44.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ D. O. Bolander et. al. (eds.), *New Webster's Dictionary of English Language* [International Edition,

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The age of discovery witnessed a broad change in globalization. This was a period when for the first time, Eurasia¹⁰ and Africa were engaged in substantial cultural, material and biologic exchange with the New world. Thus, in the 15th century, the two kingdoms of the Iberian Peninsula namely; Portugal and Castile sent the first exploratory voyages around the Horn of Africa and to the Americas which Christopher Columbus discovered in 1492. It's noteworthy to mention that global integration continued with the European colonization of the Americas and this covers the period between 15th century and 18th century.¹¹ The 19th century ushered in globalization in its modern form. Globalization in the period was decisively shaped by 19th century imperialism. As a result of the opium wars¹² and the completion of the British conquest of India, vast population of these regions were subjected to ready consumers of European exports. Again; during this period, the areas of sub-Sahara Africa and Pacific islands became incorporated into the world system and the European conquest of the new dominions especially sub-Sahara Africa yielded valuable natural resources and helped to accelerate trade and investment opportunities between the European imperial powers and their colonies and the United States.

However, at the beginning of the 20th century which witnessed World War I¹³ the first phase of modern globalization started to breakdown. Globalization¹⁴ in the period since World War II,¹⁵ was primarily the result of planning by economists, business interests and politicians who become aware of the cost implications associated with protectionism and declining international economic integration. Their efforts resulted to the Bretton Woods Conferences and the formation of global institutions intended to oversee the renewed process of globalization. Among these International institutions are the International Bank for Reconstruction and development (the World Bank) and the International Monetary fund.

Since World War II, barriers to international commerce have been reduced through international agreements such as GATT.¹⁶ Among the initiatives carried out as a result of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade and the World Trade Organization which is the successor of General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade includes the promotion of free trade by the elimination of tariff, reduction of transportation costs etc, and restriction of free trade by the harmonization of intellectual property law across the majority of states, with more restrictions and the supranational recognition of intellectual property restriction. Thus for instance, patents granted by China would be recognized in the United States. In this process of globalization, there is an easy movement of products and financial flows across borders involving investments, financial capital, merchandise trade, services, technology and labour. Competition, production and markets become global in outlook, while goods and services become less distinguishable with their country of origin, hence there is internationalization or a globalization of consumption as consumers are buying more foreign goods.¹⁷

4.0. NIGERIA'S ENGAGEMENTS

The Nigeria's engagement with the globalization process has entailed its adoption of the tenets of neo-liberal economic policies of liberalization, privatization, deregulation and the 'opening-up' of the economic space by offering incentives to foreign investors to invest in the country. The Nigeria's government thus enacted the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission Act, Cap.N117,Laws of the Federation of Nigeria,2004. The key provisions designed to achieve this objective, including the Hull formula on payment of compensation in cases of nationalization or expropriation. The inclusion of such provisions in the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission Act ostensibly in deference to the demands of economic globalization and the race to attract foreign investment, has facilitated the activities of transnational corporations which have relied on them to continue to violate human rights and issuance of threats to humanity in the country. This stems from the fact that the economic liberalization measures were not accompanied by corresponding regulations for transnational corporations on the respect for, and protection of human rights.

Notwithstanding such deep commitment to the neo-liberal economic project by the Nigerian government, committed human rights Non-Governmental Organizations and other social movements have increasingly deployed legal actions and mass protests as a means of constraining the deleterious effects of economic globalization on human rights in Nigeria. In this connection, cases such as *Economic and Social Rights Case*¹⁸ and *Registered Trustees of Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project v.Federal*

Lexicon International - Publishers Guild Group, (2000) 645.

¹⁰ Bolander et al (n.9) 326.

¹¹ S. David,History of Globalization (Lewis and David,2011) 10-15.

¹² Bolander et.al (n.9) 703.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ See N.O.Obiaraeri,C.Obiaraer and J.Eleonu,*New wave of Globalisation:Nature and Impact on the Contemporary Society,A Monograph(Imo State University Press,2024)*

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ (Herein refers to as General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade).

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ Communication 155/96,(2001)AHRLR 60,15th Annual Activity Report.

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*Republic of Nigeria & Another*¹⁹ open up new spaces and possibilities for a counter-hegemonic response to the neo-liberal economic policies of the Nigerian government.

Similarly, the wave of protests by women from the Niger Delta region of Nigeria against the marginalization of their social and economic rights by transnational oil corporations in the country and the national and international impacts these had, equally epitomizes the challenge of 'globalization from above' through 'globalization from below'. Although their outcomes are largely reformist in nature, these measures must be seen as incipient strategies of a counter-hegemonic challenge to neo-liberal economic globalization with tremendous potential to alter the nature and context of the globalization in Nigeria.

5.0. THE POSTULATIONS OF SANTOS AND THE NIGERIA'S SITUATIONS

Globalization has been perceived by as an imperial project of Western capitalism. The contention of scholars who belong to this school of thought is that since globalization is a neo-liberal project with pre-determined political and economic objectives, it can only lead to pervasive poverty especially in developing countries. It is argued that globalization has led to the increased gap in material welfare within and between countries and increased marginalization especially of the least fortunate elements in society. It has led to the widening of existing social and economic inequities as the poor are getting poorer at a faster rate.²⁰

To be sure and arising from the operations of the current neo-liberal economic paradigm, the words of Santos has become very apposite particularly as it pertains to Nigeria. According to him, 'People are not poor, they are impoverished; they do not starve, they are starved; they are not marginal, they are marginalized; they are not victims, they are victimized.'²¹ Nigerians have been impoverished through the forceful use of natural resources by the Nigerian government. The citizens have been starved and marginalized by the Federal Government of Nigeria.

It has also been argued that the adoption of neo-liberal globalization has led to the emergence in several countries of what Santos calls 'a new global social apartheid'. This is manifest in the dichotomy between the developed and developing countries and within a country, between the few wealthy and the poor majority.

In the context of Nigeria, the dichotomy is so prominent that a large majority of ordinary Nigerians, now feed from dump sites, while the few political and economic elites pre-occupy themselves with acquiring properties and erecting pent houses in foreign countries. It must be mentioned that these negative impacts are usually felt the more by the down trodden masses who do not have decent paying jobs, and who are usually the prime targets when companies and governments have to down-size their work force. Recognizing these challenges and the consequences of neo-liberal globalization, Stiglitz argues for the reshaping and restructuring of globalization to enable it serve the best interests of human kind.²²

However, these challenges will be significantly obliterated with the adoption of counter-hegemonic globalization. This is the form of globalization that works with, and for the people, and deploys the principles of participatory democracy as distinct from the Western form of representative democracy being globalized today under the false rubric of 'democracy'. It is driven by those that have been victimized and marginalized by neo-liberal globalization. It is only the adoption of this form of globalization that can facilitate the emancipation of the ordinary masses in Nigeria from the oppression and marginalization of the ruling elite.

6.0. CONCLUSION

It is in recognition of the manifest inadequacies of hegemonic globalization that this paper had called for the option of counter-hegemonic globalization and its application in Nigeria. It is the contention of this paper that such an approach will enable Nigeria to deal with the challenges posed by contemporary globalization. This is because counter-hegemonic globalization springs from the shared experiences of people everywhere. Indeed, it speaks of, and speaks to the down-trodden masses who struggle on a daily basis to 'eke' out a living.

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¹⁹ Suit No.ECW/CCJ/APP/08, Ruling delivered on the 12/10/2009.

²⁰ O.O Ajayi, *Globalization and the Politics of Marginality*, O. Vaughan, et al (eds.) *Globalization and Marginalization*, (Sefer Books Ltd, 2005) 201-235, 215.

²¹ B.Santos, *Towards a New Legal Common Sense: Law, Globalization and Emancipation* (Butterworths, 2002) 289.

²² J. Stiglitz, *Making Globalization Work*, (Penguin Books, 2006) 24.

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